

Synthesis and Characterization of A Binuclear Zinc Complex ([LZn₂(OAc)₂][PF₆]), A Pentadentate Phenol-Based Ligand: A Synthetic Model for the Active Sites of Dizinc Hydrolases

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Abstract: This article presents the synthesis and characterization of a new zinc(II) complex, ([LZn₂(OAc)₂][PF₆]), prepared from a pentadentate phenolic ligand: 4-(tert-butyl)-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino)methyl)phenol(L). The ligand was obtained by a condensation reaction between 5-tert-butyl-2-hydroxybenzene-1,3-dialdehyde and N,N-dimethylethane-1,2-diamine with a yield of 88 %.

The formation of the complex, obtained with a yield of 94 %, was confirmed by various spectroscopic methods (IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR) as well as by mass spectrometry (HRMS).

X-ray diffraction analysis reveals a unique structure where each metal center is coordinated by two nitrogen atoms and the phenolic oxygen of the ligand, which acts as a bridge between the two zinc ions. A Hirshfeld surface analysis was performed to quantify intermolecular interactions within the crystal lattice, highlighting the predominance of H...H contacts (50.5 %) and the stabilising role of O-H...H hydrogen bonds. O bonds. This complex is a relevant synthetic model for studying the active sites of dizinc hydrolases, such as aminopeptidases or alkaline phosphatases.

Keywords: Ligands, Complexes, characterisation, Hirshfeld surface, Spectroscopic.

1. Introduction

Phenol-based ligands are often used to stabilize dinuclear metal cores.^{1,2,3}

Due to the interesting properties resulting from the proximity of the two metal centers, extensive research has been conducted on bimetallic complexes.⁴

These studies focus on magnetic, electronic, spectroscopic, and structural properties, as well as reactivity.^{5,6}

Binuclear zinc complexes have attracted particular interest as important structural mimics of the active site of a range of metalloenzymes, such as zinc-dependent aminopeptidases, metallo-beta-lactamases, and alkaline phosphatases.^{7,8,9,10,11,12,13}

The synthesis and characterization of a binuclear Zn complex ([LZn₂(OAc)₂][PF₆]) from the pentadentate ligand 4-(tert-butyl)-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino)methyl)phenol (L) using IR spectroscopy, multinuclear NMR, and high-resolution mass spectrometry methods are reported in this study.

The crystal structure was solved by X-ray diffraction, allowing the coordination mode of the ligand and the geometry around the zinc centers to be elucidated. Finally, an in-depth study of Hirshfeld surfaces is presented to analyze the crystal stacking and the nature of the non-covalent interactions stabilizing the structure.

2. Results and Discussion

The synthesis of the pentadentate ligand, 4-(tert-butyl)-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino) - methyl)phenol (L) was achieved by condensation of N,N-dimethylethane-1,2-diamine with 5-tert-butyl-2-hydroxybenzene-1,3-dialdehyde in the presence of NH_4PF_6 in ethanol at reflux (80°C) (Scheme 1). Ligand L was obtained with a yield of 88 %.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of the ligand (L)

In the IR spectrum of the ligand, we find a band at 1638 cm^{-1} attributed to the imine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibration, and the absence of a band corresponding to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration of the precursor 5-tert-butyl-2-hydroxybenzene-1,3-dialdehyde of the ligand. 14

In the ^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand, we observe two triplets at 2.64 ppm and 3.74 ppm attributed respectively to the $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}(\text{Me})_2$ and $=\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ protons, and a singlet at 8.57 ppm attributed to the imine protons.

On the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, we also observe signals at 162.0 ppm and 45.8 ppm attributed respectively to carbons, $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ and $-\text{N}(\text{Me})_2$.

The HRMS (m/z) mass spectrum of the ligand reveals the presence of a peak at 347.2801, corresponding to the molecular mass of the ligand.

This information confirms the formation of the ligand.

The complex $([\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6])$ was synthesized from the ligand 4-(tert-butyl)-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino)methyl)phenol and zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Scheme 2) at room temperature in the presence of KPF6 in methanol for 2 h. The complex was obtained with a yield of 94%.

Scheme 2: Synthesis of the complex $([\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6])$

On the ^1H NMR spectrum of the complex, we observe that the signal of the $-\text{CH}_2-\text{N}$ protons is unshielded by +0.16 ppm and that of the $=\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ protons by +0.19 ppm.

The imine protons have also undergone shielding of -0.03 ppm.

We also observe signals at 172.75 ppm (OAc) and 22.96 ppm (OAc) attributed to acetates (OAc) on the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the complex.

The mass spectrum of the HRMS complex (m/z) reveals the presence of a peak at 591.1519, corresponding to the experimental molecular mass of the complex.

The structure characterized by X-ray diffraction shows two metal centers where each zinc atom is bound to the ligand by two nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom.

All of this information gathered on the spectra shows that there is coordination of the ligand with two zinc centers, and this is confirmed by the structure of the complex (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Structure of the complex ($[LZn_2(OAc)_2][PF_6]$)

X-ray Crystallography

Crystal structure description

The crystal structure of the compound with formula $C_{49}H_{79}Cl_3F_{12}N_8O_{10}P_2Zn_4$ was determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction and refined by the full least squares method on F^2 using the SHELXL program.

The Mercury and Diamond programs were used for modeling, allowing detailed visualization of the three-dimensional structure of the complex ($[LZn_2(OAc)_2][PF_6]$).^{15,16} The conditions for recording and refining this compound are summarized in Table 3.

The compound crystallizes in the triclinic system with the centro-symmetric space group $P\bar{1}(N^{\circ}2)$. The complex is a dinuclear zinc(II) entity. The structure contains two independent dinuclear units in the asymmetric unit (labeled Zn1-Zn2 and Zn3-Zn4), associated with polyfunctional organic ligands containing hydrogen bond donor atoms O and N, as well as chloride counterions and fluorinated groups (Figure 2). The overall structure consists of discrete electrically neutral molecular units, stacked periodically in the crystal lattice (Figure 5).

Figure 2: Representation of the asymmetric unit of the dinuclear zinc(II) complex $[LZn_2(OAc)_2][PF_6]$

The presence of the inversion center of the $P\bar{1}$ space group implies that the metal aggregate is either entirely contained within the asymmetric unit or partially generated by symmetry, leading to a centrosymmetric molecular organization in the lattice.

The P1-centered anion has an irregular octahedral geometry with well-defined P-F bonds (Table 2). The P2-centered anion exhibits marked crystallographic disorder, illustrated by the multiplication of fluorine atom positions (F9A, F9B, F10A, etc.), indicating rotation or instability of the ion in the crystal lattice (Figure 3). Chloroform (CHCl_3) molecules are also present in the lattice, acting as a crystallization solvent to fill structural voids.

Figure 3: Geometric environment of hexafluorophosphate anions (P1 and P2) in the crystal structure of $[\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6]$ Coordination environment of Zn(II) centers

In the complex, each zinc metal center is pentacoordinated. The coordination environment for each metal (e.g., Zn1) consists of two nitrogen atoms (N1, N2) from the ligand's side arms and a bridging oxygen atom (O1) connecting the two centers Zn1 and Zn2. This oxygen appears to originate from a phenolate group central to the ligand and two oxygen atoms (O3, O5) from a carboxylate group (probably an acetate) that bridges the two metal centers in an $\eta^1:\eta^1:\mu_2$ -syn-syn manner.

The geometry around zinc forms a distorted coordination polyhedron (trigonal bipyramid type) Figure 4 and Table 1, illustrating the characteristic structural flexibility of zinc.

Figure 4: Representation of the coordination polyhedron (left) and structural environment (right) of the Zn(II) centers in the $[\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6]$ complex.

Table 1: Experimental geometric parameters of the pentacoordinated coordination environments of Zn(II) metal centres in $([\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6])$

Zn1—O5	1.9746 (16)	Zn3—O10	1.9812 (17)
Zn1—O3	1.9861 (15)	Zn3—O8	1.9873 (16)
Zn1—N1	2.0298 (19)	Zn3—N7	2.0319 (19)

Zn1—O1	2.0862 (14)	Zn3—O6	2.0789 (15)
Zn1—N2	2.2023 (18)	Zn3—N8	2.1781 (19)
Zn2—O2	1.9691 (15)	Zn4—O7	1.9657 (17)
Zn2—O4	1.9841 (16)	Zn4—O9	1.9733 (18)
Zn2—N3	2.0253 (18)	Zn4—N5	1.999 (2)
Zn2—O1	2.1062 (14)	Zn4—O6	2.1149 (14)
Zn2—N4	2.2154 (18)	Zn4—N6	2.239 (2)
O5—Zn1—O3	110.84 (7)	O10—Zn3—O8	114.76 (8)
O5—Zn1—N1	110.98 (7)	O10—Zn3—N7	111.85 (8)
O3—Zn1—N1	136.82 (8)	O8—Zn3—N7	132.54 (8)
O5—Zn1—O1	100.32 (6)	O10—Zn3—O6	97.49 (7)
O3—Zn1—O1	94.30 (6)	O8—Zn3—O6	94.08 (6)
N1—Zn1—O1	88.47 (6)	N7—Zn3—O6	88.31 (7)
O5—Zn1—N2	91.47 (7)	O10—Zn3—N8	93.20 (7)
O3—Zn1—N2	88.79 (7)	O8—Zn3—N8	87.96 (7)
N1—Zn1—N2	79.88 (7)	N7—Zn3—N8	80.98 (8)
O1—Zn1—N2	165.80 (6)	O6—Zn3—N8	167.09 (7)
O2—Zn2—O4	110.59 (7)	O7—Zn4—O9	115.66 (8)
O2—Zn2—N3	114.92 (7)	O7—Zn4—N5	117.78 (10)
O4—Zn2—N3	133.61 (7)	O9—Zn4—N5	125.89 (10)
O2—Zn2—O1	97.50 (6)	O7—Zn4—O6	97.06 (6)
O4—Zn2—O1	94.60 (6)	O9—Zn4—O6	93.60 (7)
N3—Zn2—O1	88.13 (6)	N5—Zn4—O6	87.90 (7)
O2—Zn2—N4	96.36 (7)	O7—Zn4—N6	91.78 (9)
O4—Zn2—N4	85.86 (7)	O9—Zn4—N6	89.89 (9)
N3—Zn2—N4	80.83 (7)	N5—Zn4—N6	80.74 (8)
O1—Zn2—N4	164.99 (6)	O6—Zn4—N6	167.97 (7)

Conversely, the presence of shorter side arms on the ligand exerts steric constraints on the two zinc ions: it prevents them from coming closer together and imposes significantly greater distances Z1...Z2 (3.2 Å).¹⁷ This structural separation prevents the small hydroxide group from simultaneously bridging the two metals Figure 4 (right).

Figure 5: Molecular architecture of the complex with Zn(II) metal centers coordinated by acetate ligands in the lattice.

Table 2: P–F bond lengths (Å) and F–P–F coordination angles (°) in the phosphorus coordination polyhedron.

Phosphorus coordination polyhedron			
P1—F1	1.582 (2)	P2—F10A	1.559 (17)
P1—F2	1.5834 (18)	P2—F11B	1.561 (6)
P1—F4	1.585 (2)	P2—F9B	1.577 (8)
P1—F3	1.592 (2)	P2—F11A	1.584 (15)
P1—F5	1.6088 (19)	P2—F8	1.5977 (16)
P2—F12A	1.490 (11)	P2—F7	1.5996 (15)
P2—F9A	1.507 (13)	P2—F12B	1.612 (7)
P2—F10B	1.536 (8)		
F6—P1—F1	89.21 (14)	F10A—P2—F11A	87.2 (10)
F6—P1—F2	179.47 (15)	F12A—P2—F8	87.2 (6)
F1—P1—F2	90.45 (14)	F9A—P2—F8	91.7 (7)
F6—P1—F4	90.78 (13)	F10B—P2—F8	90.1 (4)
F1—P1—F4	178.29 (15)	F10A—P2—F8	91.5 (8)
F2—P1—F4	89.58 (13)	F11B—P2—F8	91.5 (3)
F6—P1—F3	89.75 (13)	F9B—P2—F8	89.0 (4)
F1—P1—F3	92.06 (15)	F11A—P2—F8	89.1 (6)
F2—P1—F3	89.86 (12)	F12A—P2—F7	92.3 (6)
F4—P1—F3	89.65 (13)	F9A—P2—F7	88.5 (7)
F6—P1—F5	90.71 (12)	F10B—P2—F7	90.3 (4)
F1—P1—F5	88.67 (13)	F10A—P2—F7	89.0 (8)
F2—P1—F5	89.69 (10)	F11B—P2—F7	88.2 (3)
F4—P1—F5	89.62 (12)	F9B—P2—F7	91.3 (4)
F3—P1—F5	179.14 (12)	F11A—P2—F7	90.8 (6)
F12A—P2—F9A	94.1 (11)	F8—P2—F7	179.47 (10)
F12A—P2—F10A	177.3 (11)	F10B—P2—F12B	178.3 (5)
F9A—P2—F10A	88.3 (11)	F11B—P2—F12B	88.7 (5)
F10B—P2—F11B	92.7 (6)	F9B—P2—F12B	87.8 (5)
F10B—P2—F9B	90.7 (6)	F8—P2—F12B	90.8 (4)
F11B—P2—F9B	176.6 (5)	F7—P2—F12B	88.8 (4)
F12A—P2—F11A	90.4 (9)		

Hirshfeld surface analysis

The Hirshfeld surface represents the region in space where molecules come into contact. The representation of the Hirshfeld surface of the asymmetric unit complex highlights intermolecular interactions in the crystal structure (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Hirshfeld Surface around the LZn₂(OAc) moieties of the asymmetric unit. The surface is colored according to the inner chemical type: hydrogen H-C: grey, hydrogen H-O: blue, carbon: black, oxygen: red)

The 2D graphs of the Hirshfeld surface fingerprints highlight the atoms involved in the contacts (Figure 7). The graph shown in Figure 7a represents the reciprocal H...O/O...H contacts. It is characterised by two symmetrical peaks at a short distance $d_i+d_e \sim 1.7$ Å. These peaks are characteristic of the strong O-H...O hydrogen bond present in the structure, which accounts for 9.1% of the total surface area, but there are also C-H...O contacts at a longer distance. The graph in Figure 7d representing H...H contacts is characterised by an end pointing towards the origin along the diagonal corresponding to $d_i = d_e \sim 1.15$ Å. They represent 50.5% of Hirshfeld's total surface area. C...H / H...C contacts represent 11.6% of intermolecular contacts Figure 7e. The decomposition of the 2D fingerprint also shows other contacts: F...H/ H...F (20.1%), which is a major reciprocal contact, and Cl.../ H...Cl, which is also an important contact with 5.2%. Hydrogen bond-type interactions representing reciprocal H...O/O...H contacts would constitute the strongest interactions, stabilising the crystal stacking.

Figure 7: Fingerprint plots in (d_i, d_e) of the main contacts on the Hirshfeld surface. The graphs were obtained with CrystalExplorer17 program.¹⁸

Table 3: Crystal data and structure parameters of the complex

Parameter	Value
Chemical formula	$C_{49}H_{79}Cl_3F_{12}N_8O_{10}P_2Zn_4$
Molecular weight ($g \cdot mol^{-1}$)	1597.97
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, $P\overline{1}$
Temperature (K)	150
a, b, c (Å)	10.2306 (3), 14.7547 (5), 22.3747 (7)
α, β, γ ($^\circ$)	94.515 (2), 94.496 (2), 92.580 (2)
Volume (\AA^3); Z	3352.15 (18); 2
Radiation type	Mo K α
Wavelength (Å)	0.7107
Diffractometer	Bruker APEX-II CCD
Measured reflections	51128
Independent reflections	14051
Observed reflections [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	12446
Tmin, Tmax ($^\circ$)	2.3, 26.7
No. of measured reflections (alt.)	15,823

Rint (%)	2.9
$\sin\theta_{\max}/\lambda$ (\AA^{-1})	0.63
wR ₂ [$F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)$]	0.032
wR(F^2)	0.089
Goodness of fit (gof)	1.07
No. of reflections (refinement)	14051
No. of parameters	886
H-atom treatment	Constrained
$\Delta\rho_{\max}, \Delta\rho_{\min}$ ($e \text{\AA}^{-3}$)	0.87, -0.57

Computer programs: Bruker APEX2, Bruker SAINT, SHELXS97 (Sheldrick, 2010), SHELXL2013 (Sheldrick, 2013), Bruker SHELXTL.

Table 4: Geometric details of hydrogen bonds (\AA , $^\circ$) (D-donor; A-acceptor; H-hydrogen) of the complex and symmetry code of acceptor atom

D—H \cdots A	D—H	H \cdots A	D \cdots A	D—H \cdots A
C41—H41A \cdots F4 ⁱ	0.99	2.48	3.326 (3)	143.6
C31—H31 \cdots F5 ⁱⁱ	0.95	2.44	3.377 (3)	170.7
C31—H31 \cdots F2 ⁱⁱ	0.95	2.61	3.188 (3)	119.3
C12—H12 \cdots F11B ⁱⁱⁱ	0.95	2.55	3.076 (8)	114.9
C12—H12 \cdots F11A ⁱⁱⁱ	0.95	2.47	2.996 (16)	114.7
C12—H12 \cdots F8 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.95	2.50	3.439 (3)	167.8
C24—H24A \cdots O1 ^{iv}	0.98	2.41	3.334 (3)	156.4
C7—H7 \cdots F7	0.95	2.48	3.353 (3)	152.3
C13—H13B \cdots F12B	0.99	2.45	3.263 (10)	138.5
C14—H14A \cdots F6 ⁱⁱ	0.99	2.57	3.254 (3)	126.5
C16—H16C \cdots O5	0.98	2.62	3.139 (3)	113.0
C44—H44A \cdots O10	0.98	2.59	3.160 (3)	117.3
C15—H15A \cdots O3	0.98	2.61	3.104 (3)	111.1
C40A—H40C \cdots F10A	0.98	2.23	3.05 (3)	139.7
C40A—H40C \cdots F7	0.98	2.58	3.416 (14)	142.9
C39A—H39B \cdots O7	0.98	2.65	3.160 (11)	112.6
C37A—H37A \cdots Cl2 ^v	0.99	2.92	3.596 (12)	126.5
C41—H41A \cdots F4 ⁱ	0.99	2.48	3.326 (3)	143.6
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Symmetry codes: (i) $-x, -y+1, -z+2$; (ii) $x, y-1, z$; (iii) $-x+1, -y+1, -z+1$; (iv) $-x+1, -y, -z+1$; (v) $x-1, y, z$; (vi) $-x, -y+1, -z+1$.

Hexafluorophosphate anions actively participate in supramolecular architecture via numerous C—H···F interactions. H···F distances range from 2.23 to 2.65 Å, while the corresponding D···A distances range from 2.996(16) to 3.439 (3) Å, with D—H···A angles ranging from 114.7 to 170.7°. Some interactions are relatively directional (e.g. C31—H31···F5ⁱⁱ, 170.7°), suggesting a significant contribution to the cohesion of the crystal lattice (Table 4).

The halogenated solvent molecules are stabilised in the crystal cavities by C—H···Cl contacts, notably C37A—H37A···Cl2^v, characterised by an H···Cl distance of 2.92 Å, a D···A distance of 3.596(12) Å and an angle of 126.5°, consistent with a weak but structuring interaction (Table 4). All of these secondary interactions generate a dense, well-ordered three-dimensional architecture in which the dinuclear entities remain discrete from the point of view of metal coordination, but are linked together by an extensive network of weak hydrogen interactions and contacts involving fluorine and chlorine atoms. These interactions ensure overall cohesion and optimise the efficiency of crystal stacking.

3. Experimental Section

You will find all the experimental details concerning the synthesis of the ligand and the complex.

Ligand. In a flask equipped with a stirrer and a condenser, 5-chloro-2-hydroxyisophthalaldehyde (100 mg; 0.543 mmol) in 20 mL of absolute ethanol and N,N-dimethylethylene-1,2-diamine (0.12 mL; 1.196 mmol) and 10% mol NH_4PF_6 are added to a flask equipped with a stirrer and a condenser. The mixture is heated to reflux (80 °C) and stirred for 2 hours. After cooling, the solvent is evaporated using a rotary evaporator. The product obtained is dissolved in ether. After concentration and vacuum drying, a yellow paste is obtained with a yield of 88%.

RMN ^1H (400MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.58 (s, 2H, -CH=N), 7.66 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 3.74 (t, J=6.8Hz, 2H), 2.64 (t, J=6.9Hz, 2H), 2.30 (s, 12H, -N-(CH_3)₄), 1.29 (s, 9H, -C-tBu) ppm.

RMN ^{13}C (400MHz, CDCl_3): δ 162.0, 159.8, 140.9, 129.2, 121.0, 65.9, 60.0, 45.8, 34.10, 31.4 ppm.

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 2948, 2818, 2767, 2346, 2115, 1637, 1599, 1457, 1361, 1262, 1225, 1184, 1155, 1120, 1041, 991, 882, 842, 782, 761, 709 cm^{-1} .

HRMS (m/z): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{35}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: 347.2811; found : 347.2801.

($[\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6]$). In a flask, 4-chloro-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino)phenol (50 mg, 0.154 mmol), zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (67 mg, 0.308 mmol) and KPF_6 (53 mg, 0.154 mmol) were dissolved in 5 mL of methanol. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. After concentrating the solution by half, diethyl ether was added until a precipitate formed. After filtration, the orange-coloured solid is recovered with a yield of 92% and then recrystallised by slow diffusion in a chloroform-pentane mixture.

RMN ^1H (400MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.55 (s, 2H, -CH=N), 7.50 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 3.83 (t, 4H, =N- CH_2 -), 2.80 (t, 4H, - CH_2 -N), 2.45 (s, 12H, -N-(CH_3)₄), 2.02 (s, 6H, OAc), 1.28 (s, 9H, C-tBu) ppm.

RMN ^{13}C (400MHz, CDCl_3): δ 178.78 ($\text{C}_{\text{Ar-O}}$), 172.75 (OAc), 166.53 (C=N), 140.24 (Ar), 139.07 (Ar), 120.48 (Ar), 57.61 (NCH₂), 52.42 (NCH₂), 45.47 (NMe₂), 33.69 (C-tBu), 31.07 (C du tBu), 22.96 (OAc) ppm.

HRMS (m/z): $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ calculated $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{39}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Zn}_2$: 591.1503; found: 591.1519.

4. Conclusion

We synthesised a binuclear Zn complex ($[\text{LZn}_2(\text{OAc})_2][\text{PF}_6]$) from the pentadentate ligand 4-(tert-butyl)-2,6-bis((E)-((2-(dimethylamino)ethyl)imino)methyl)phenol (L) with high yields. Comprehensive characterisation by spectroscopy and mass spectrometry confirmed the formation of the products, while X-ray diffraction accurately established the binuclear structure in which the ligand connects the two zinc centres. Hirshfeld surface analysis identified H...H contacts and hydrogen bonds as the key interactions ensuring the stability of the crystal structure.

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